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Title: The Hospital de Santo António in times of epidemics: vulnerability and resilience in Porto of eight hundred (1850-1900)

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Abstract: The nineteenth century in the city of Porto was particularly turbulent and challenging for its inhabitants, as their experiences were marked by a series of adverse events, including wars, social unrest, and devastating epidemics. Collectively and individually, these events had a profound impact on Porto society, exposing numerous problems and social inequalities. It was in this scenario of great vulnerability that epidemics took the heaviest toll, testing the effectiveness of healthcare structures and often requiring dramatic interventions by administrative authorities. While authorities strove to implement sanitary measures to control outbreaks and prevent their spread within the city, hospitals took in patients and sought to treat them with the human and financial resources at their disposal. The Hospital de Santo António, founded in 1770 by the Santa Casa da Misericórdia do Porto, was regarded as the largest and most important hospital in the city. This study aims to analyze the hospital's response during

epidemic crises by examining the measures and procedures adopted, the regulations established, the available resources for treatment, clinical and nursing staff, and physical infrastructure. Additionally, it seeks to identify weaknesses and constraints, as well as recurring practices or improvements in resilience. This research is based on a cross-analysis of bibliographical and documentary sources, particularly the reports of the Santa Casa da Misericórdia do Porto.

Keywords: Epidemics; Vulnerability; Resilience; Hospital de Santo António; Porto.